

energy homeostasis associated / adropin (ENHO) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid : 0000-0001-7027-5788

104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Abstract

Background : Adropin encoded by ENHO in humans, is highly conserved across mammals. It was identified as a protein hormone (hepatokine) secreted from the liver, which played a role in obesity and energy homeostasis. "Adropin" derives from the Latin words "aduro" (to set fire to) and "pinguis" (fat). It is implicated in obstructive sleep apnea, colostrum, transitional and mature milk and plasma in lactating women, cardiovascular diseases, inhibition of water drinking, enzyme-positive acute coronary syndrome, Myeloperoxidase (MPO) anti-neutrophil cytoplasm autoantibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis, hemodialysis, systemic sclerosis, diabetic nephropathy and type 2 diabetes mellitus, preeclampsia, osteoarthritis, alcoholic liver cirrhosis, Prader-Willi syndrome, human skeletal muscle feed arteries, age-related vascular dysfunction, psoriasis vulgaris, adiposity, type 2 diabetes, cancer, colitis and subarachnoid hemorrhage, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of ENHO, some of which have been known to exist via

^{*}ML dicoveries of ENHO synergy in Meningiomas

Email address: sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com (shriprakash sinha)

¹©Shriprakash Sinha

wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: ENHO, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Meningioma	2
1.1.1	World Health Organization (WHO) classification	3
1.1.2	Historical perspective	3
1.1.3	Pathophysiology	4
1.2	energy homeostasis associated (ENHO)	4
1.3	Roles of ENHO in different disease	5
1.4	Insight behind the work	9
1.5	Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	9
2	Methods	10
2.1	Static data from Patel et al. [1]	10
2.2	Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	10
2.3	Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	11
2.4	Regarding biological insight	11
3	Results & Discussion	12
3.1	ENHO related synergies	12
3.1.1	ENHO - individual genes	12
4	Conclusion	15

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. energy homeostasis associated (ENHO)

Obesity and nutrient homeostasis are linked by mechanisms that are not fully elucidated. Kumar et al. [13] described a secreted protein, adropin, encoded by a gene

ENHO, which was expressed in liver and brain. They observed that lean C57BL/6J mice fed high-fat diet (HFD) exhibited a rapid increase, while fasting reduced expression of liver ENHO, compared to controls. Further, ENHO expression declined with diet-induced obesity (DIO) associated with 3 months of HFD or with genetically induced obesity, which suggested an association with metabolic disorders in the obese state. In DIO mice, they found that transgenic overexpression or systemic adropin treatment weakened hepatosteatosis and insulin resistance independently of effects on adiposity or food intake. Also, they observed that adropin regulated expression of hepatic lipogenic genes and adipose tissue peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ , a major regulator of lipogenesis. Thus they hypothesized that adropin might be a factor governing glucose and lipid homeostasis, which protected against hepatosteatosis and hyperinsulinemia associated with obesity.

Lovren et al. [14] hypothesized that adropin might exert direct effects on the endothelium and for this they partnered in vitro cell culture models with an in vivo murine injury model to determine the potential vascular effects of adropin. They observed that adropin was expressed in human umbilical vein and coronary artery endothelial cells (ECs). Further, adropin-treated endothelial cells showed greater proliferation, migration and capillary-like tube formation and less permeability and TNF- α induced apoptosis. In keeping with a vascular protective effect, adropin stimulated Akt Ser(473) and endothelial nitric oxide (NO) synthase Ser(1177) phosphorylation. Finally, adropin improved murine limb perfusion and elevated capillary density following induction of hindlimb ischemia. In conclusion, they reported a potential endothelial protective role of adropin that is likely mediated via upregulation of endothelial NO synthase expression through the VEGFR2-phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase-Akt and VEGFR2-extracellular signal regulated kinase 1/2 pathways.

1.3. Roles of ENHO in different disease

Gozal et al. [15] tested the hypothesis that concentrations of adropin, are lower in **obstructive sleep apnea** (OSA) or not, especially when associated with endothelial dysfunction. They reported reduced plasma adropin concentrations in pediatric OSA when endothelial dysfunction was present, and returned to within normal values after adenotonsillectomy. They concluded that assessment of circulating adropin concentrations might provide a reliable indicator of vascular injury in the context of OSA in children.

Aydin et al. [16] compared copeptin, adropin and irisin concentrations between **colostrum, transitional and mature milk and plasma in lactating women** with and without GDM and these values with those from non-lactating women. For this, the collected venous blood samples before suckling from 15 healthy lactating women aged 26-30 years, 15 lactating women with GDM aged 26-32 years, and 14 age-matched controls aged 25-31 years. Further, they collected colostrum, transitional milk and mature milk samples just before suckling. They found increased levels of copeptin, adropin and irisin in the colostrum than those in transitional and mature milk samples from healthy women; also, transitional milk had higher copeptin, adropin and irisin concentrations than mature milk. Further, the amounts of copeptin in the colostrum and transitional milk were significantly higher than in mature milk samples from women

with GDM, while the amounts of adropin and irisin were significantly lower. Thus they hypothesized that these peptides could influence the regulation of metabolic pathways and the postnatal growth and development of different organs in the newborn.

Cardiovascular diseases, such as atherosclerosis and hypertension, are the major cause of mortality and morbidity in the world. Li et al. [17], in their review, summarized recent data suggesting the roles of adropin in several major **cardiovascular diseases**. Increasing evidence suggests that adropin is a potential regulator of cardiovascular functions and plays a protective role in the pathogenesis and development of cardiovascular diseases.

Stein et al. [18] described a central nervous system action of adropin to **inhibit water drinking** and identified a potential adropin receptor, the orphan G protein-coupled receptor, GPR19. They observed that reduction in GPR19 mRNA levels in medial basal hypothalamus of male rats resulted in the loss of the inhibitory effect of adropin on water deprivation-induced thirst.

Enzyme-positive acute coronary syndrome (EPACS) can cause injury to or death of the heart muscle owing to prolonged ischaemia. Research has indicated that in addition to liver and brain cells, cardiomyocytes also produce adropin. Aydin et al. [19] hypothesized that adropin is released into the bloodstream during myocardial injury caused by acute coronary syndrome (ACS), so serum and saliva levels rise as the myocytes die. Therefore, it could be useful to investigate how ACS affects the timing and significance of adropin release in human subjects. They found that serum adropin, troponin I, CK and CK-MB concentrations in the EPACS group became gradually higher than those in the control group up to six hours, and troponin I continued to rise up to 12 hours after EPACS. Further, the same relative increase in adropin level was observed in the saliva.

Myeloperoxidase (MPO) anti-neutrophil cytoplasm autoantibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis commonly causes life-threatening pulmonary alveolar hemorrhage or fibrosis. Gao et al. [20] investigated the importance of ENHO mutations and adropin deficiency in the development of MPO-ANCA associated lung injury. They observed lower concentration of serum adropin in patients than that of the healthy subjects, especially those with ENHO mutations. Further in vivo, homo- and heterozygous carriers of the null adropin allele exhibited MPO-ANCA associated pulmonary alveolar hemorrhage as compared to wild-type mice. Thus their findings indicated that the presence of ENHO mutations or adropin-deficiency was a probable molecular basis for the initial events triggered in MPO-ANCA associated lung injury.

Grzegorzewska et al. [21] examined the involvement of plasma adropin and adropin-associated genes (ENHO and RXRA) in metabolic abnormalities of **hemodialysis (HD)** patients. They observed that HD patients showed lower circulating adropin concentration compared with controls. In dyslipidemic patients, plasma adropin was lower than that in non-dyslipidemics, but it was not significantly different in diabetics vs. non-diabetics or in patients with or without metabolic syndrome. Major homozygotes of ENHO rs2281997 seemed to have higher circulating adropin, whereas major homozygotes of RXRA (rs749759, rs10776909) showed lower levels. Major homozygotes of ENHO rs2281997 showed borderline lower insulin resistance compared with bearers of the minor allele.

Yolbas et al. [22] investigated serum adropin levels and ENHO gene expressions in

systemic sclerosis (SSc) characterized by vasculopathy, inflammation, and progressive fibrosis of the skin and internal organs. Their study included 27 patients with SSc, 39 patients with Behet's disease (BD), and 20 healthy controls (HC). The serum adropin levels were higher in the SSc and BD groups than in the HC group. They hypothesized that the augmented serum adropin levels might be expected in the chronic inflammatory disease and seem not to be characteristic of only SSc.

Hu and Chen [23] aimed to determine the correlation of serum adropin concentrations with **diabetic nephropathy** (DN). Their study consisted of 245 patients with **type 2 diabetes mellitus** (T2DM) and 81 healthy subjects. The T2DM patients were divided into normoalbuminuria, microalbuminuria, and macroalbuminuria subgroups based on urine albumin to creatinine ratio (ACR). They found lower serum adropin concentrations in T2DM than those in the controls. T2DM patients with macroalbuminuria had significantly decreased serum adropin concentrations compared with the other three groups. They concluded that serum adropin concentrations were negatively associated with renal function.

Wang et al. [24] determined serum adropin and preptin levels in 29 women with normal pregnancy and 32 women with **preeclampsia**. They found that serum adropin levels were significantly increased in women with preeclampsia compared with those with normal pregnancy but there were no significant differences in preptin levels. An increase in maternal serum adropin level was found in preeclampsia, and this may be a compensation for pregnancy complicated with preeclampsia.

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a kind of joint disease characterized by progressive joint cartilage loss and joint pain. Gundogdu and Gundogdu [25] investigated adropin and TNF- α levels and the relationship between adropin in patients with knee OA classified by Kellgren-Lawrence (KL). They found that adropin level was lower in the knee OA patients compared with the healthy controls, while TNF- α level was higher. Further, adropin level was negatively correlated with TNF- α level, blood white blood cell (WBC) count, and neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR). The consequence of their study suggested that serum adropin level could be used as a new biomarker indicating the early grade of knee OA.

Prystupa et al. [26] determined serum concentrations of afamin and adropin in patients with **alcoholic liver cirrhosis** and to define their correlation with the stage of disease. They found lower concentration of afamin in patients with compensated alcoholic liver cirrhosis, i.e. P-Ch B (85.1 ± 40.6 g/ml) and P-Ch C (56.4 ± 32.3 g/ml) individuals, compared to the control group (135.9 ± 43.6 g/ml), while for adropin, they found the highest concentration in patients with P-Ch C (11.7 ± 5.7 ng/ml) cirrhosis. They concluded that the concentration of afamin decreased with the severity of alcoholic liver cirrhosis, which most likely resulted from impaired hepatic synthesis. On the other hand, the higher the stage of disease according to the Child-Pugh score, the higher the concentration of adropin.

Orsso et al. [27] compared obestatin and adropin concentrations in younger ($n = 21$) and older children ($n = 14$) with **Prader-Willi syndrome** (PWS) and age and BMI-z-matched controls ($n = 31$). They found that fasting plasma obestatin and adropin were higher in younger children with PWS than controls and adropin was also higher in older children with PWS. Further, growth hormone treatment had no effects on obestatin or adropin in PWS. Also, adropin correlated with fasting glucose in the PWS group only.

Kwon et al. [28] determined the impact of advancing age on endogenous adropin levels in **human skeletal muscle feed arteries** (SMFAs) and the role of adropin in **age-related vascular dysfunction**. They observed that both SMFA adropin protein expression and endothelial-dependent vasodilatory function exhibited a progressive, age-related, reduction. Also, there was a strong positive correlation between SMFA adropin protein expression and both flow and ACh. A mechanistic link between adropin and nitric oxide (NO) bioavailability was supported by • increased phosphorylated endothelial NO synthase (eNOS)/eNOS protein expression with adropin incubation only in the Middle Aged and Old SMFAs; • (eNOS blockade eroding both the positive vascular effects of adropin incubation and the relationship between endothelial function and adropin protein expression and • a progressive increase in the magnitude of effect of adropin-induced eNOS-mediated vasodilatation with advancing age. Thus they concluded that adropin could be a novel therapeutic target for facilitating the restoration of endothelial function via increased NO bioavailability, with advancing age.

Korkmaz and ÖZGÜN [29] assessed serum adropin levels and their relationship with metabolic parameters in **psoriasis vulgaris** patients both with and without metabolic syndrome (MetS). They found that serum adropin levels were 2.94 ± 0.56 ng/mL in psoriatic patients without MetS, 2.49 ± 0.77 ng/mL in psoriasis patients with MetS, and 3.37 ± 0.71 ng/mL in the control group. Thus, the serum levels of adropin in psoriasis patients were significantly lower in the presence of MetS, and this decrease was more prominent than in those without MetS.

Jasaszwili et al. [30] in a review summarized and discuss the physiological, metabolic, and pathophysiological factors regulating ENHO as well as adropin and reviewed the literature addressing the role of adropin in **adiposity** and **type 2 diabetes**. Finally, they elaborated on the role of adropin in the context of the cardiovascular system, liver diseases, and **cancer**.

Liu et al. [31] described the effects of adropin deficiency on the distribution, phenotype and pathological phenotype of macrophages in colonic and mesenteric tissues of AdrKO (*Enho*^{-/-}) mice, to explore the mechanism of adropin deficiency in spontaneous and experimental **colitis**. They found that adropin levels in active UC patients were significantly lower than those in normal subjects and remission UC patients, and at the same time, a large number of proinflammatory M1-type macrophages were infiltrated in the mesenteric tissue of colonic tissues from UC and CD patients. They also observed spontaneous colitis occurrence in *Enho*^{-/-} (adropin-deficient)C57BL/6 mice, and there was an imbalance of M2 → M1 polarization of macrophages in colon and mesentery of *Enho*^{-/-} mice. In vivo, they found that adropin deficiency could worsen the pathological phenotype of colitis induced by TNBS. Thus, adropin deficiency led to an imbalance in the phenotypic distribution of macrophages infiltrating the colon and mesenteric tissues, namely, an increase in M1 type, which led to the occurrence and development of colitis.

Coşkun et al. [32] investigated early effects of exogenously administered adropin (AD) on neurological function, endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) expression, nitrite/nitrate levels, oxidative stress, and apoptosis in **subarachnoid hemorrhage** (SAH). They found that adropin administration increased brain eNOS expression, nitrite/nitrate and AD levels compared to SHAM and SAH groups. SAH produced enhanced ROS/RNS generation and reduced antioxidant capacity in the brain. Adropin

boosted brain TAC and diminished ROS/RNS production in SAH rats and no considerable change amongst SHAM and SAH + AD groups were detected. They also found that apoptotic cells were notably increased in intensity and number after SAH and were reduced by AD administration. Thus, they concluded that adropin increases eNOS expression and reduces neurobehavioral deficits, oxidative stress, and apoptotic cell death in SAH model.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [33] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [34] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular

gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [34].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [35]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [36], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is

conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [33] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [33]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [37], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological

information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. ENHO related synergies

Note - ENHO was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of ENHO were recorded.

3.1.1. ENHO - individual genes

The following genes in combination with ENHO showed high rankings - heat shock protein family B (small) member 6 (HSPB6), C-C motif chemokine ligand 26 (CCL26), flavin containing dimethylaniline monooxygenase 1 (FMO1), insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF1), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), LIM and cysteine rich domains 1 (LMCD1), glypican 4 (GPC4), integrin subunit alpha 8 (ITGA8), semaphorin 5B (SEMA5B), seizure related 6 homolog like (SEZ6L), DNA meiotic recombinase 1 (DMC1), p21 (RAC1) activated kinase 5 (PAK5), coronin 2B (CORO2B), solute carrier family 17 member 7 (SLC17A7), transmembrane protein 59 like (TMEM59L), AE binding protein 1 (AEBP1), unc-5 netrin receptor B (UNC5B), Kazal type serine peptidase inhibitor domain 1 (KAZALD1), carboxypeptidase E (CPE), tripartite motif containing 2 (TRIM2), bone marrow stromal cell antigen 1 (BST1), neurexin 2 (NRXN2), solute carrier family 35 member F2 (SLC35F2), cut like homeobox 2 (CUX2), ST8 alpha-N-acetyl-neuraminide alpha-2,8-sialyltransferase 1 (ST8SIA1), growth hormone receptor (GHR), cadherin 6 (CDH6), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), podocalyxin like 2 (PODXL2), proteoglycan 4 (PRG4), cellular communication network factor 2 (CCN2 / CTGF), tripartite motif containing 67 (TRIM67), ciliary neurotrophic factor receptor (CNTFR), basic helix-loop-helix family member e41 (BHLHE41), collagen type X alpha 1 chain (COL10A1), matrilin 4 (MATN4), neuritin 1 (NRN1), microtubule associated protein 1B (MAP1B), podocan like 1 (PODNL1), matrilin 3 (MATN3), C-type lectin domain containing 10A (CLEC10A), solute carrier family

14 member 2 (SLC14A2), contactin 6 (CNTN6), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), formin homology 2 domain containing 3 (FHOD3), Fas apoptotic inhibitory molecule 2 (FAIM2), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), forkhead box F2 (FOXF2), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 29 (TTC29), thrombospondin 1 (THBS1), semaphorin 6D (SEMA6D), NKD inhibitor of Wnt signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), forkhead associated phosphopeptide binding domain 1 (FHAD1), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), family with sequence similarity 105 member A (FAM105A), dishevelled associated activator of morphogenesis 2 (DAAM2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRN3), mohawk homeobox (MKX), ADAM metalloproteinase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 12 (ADAMTS12), VENT homeobox (VENTX), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), ABI family member 3 binding protein (ABI3BP), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), exostosin like glycosyltransferase 1 (EXTL1), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1), frizzled related protein (FRZB), NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), interleukin 17D (IL17D), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), biglycan (BGN), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), nebulin (NEB), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), sialophorin (SPN), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1) and zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings

of 2nd order combination of ENHO with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS ENHO									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T ENHO									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
HSPB6 - ENHO	365	297	247	42	CCL26 - ENHO	255	337	86	256
FMO1 - ENHO	202	97	212	351	IGF1 - ENHO	307	160	285	373
COL9A2 - ENHO	368	224	18	205	LMCD1 - ENHO	248	117	243	200
GPC4 - ENHO	215	379	51	243	ITGA8 - ENHO	279	325	69	377
SEMA5B - ENHO	297	375	111	389	SEZ6L - ENHO	358	298	286	367
DMC1 - ENHO	233	324	48	283	PAK5 - ENHO	212	7	206	341
CORO2B - ENHO	280	277	126	276	SLC17A7 - ENHO	58	367	287	320
TMEM59L - ENHO	39	360	326	275	AEBP1 - ENHO	362	166	229	369
UNC5B - ENHO	341	259	121	203	KAZALD1 - ENHO	316	300	93	288
CPE - ENHO	246	334	91	342	TRIM2 - ENHO	361	323	143	214
BST1 - ENHO	253	364	109	343	NRXN2 - ENHO	71	380	219	366
SLC35F2 - ENHO	388	230	207	232	CUX2 - ENHO	96	284	258	354
ST8SIA1 - ENHO	122	304	353	277	GHR - ENHO	303	349	35	248
CDH6 - ENHO	272	14	259	201	NPR3 - ENHO	277	361	288	44
PODXL2 - ENHO	85	342	260	249	PRG4 - ENHO	308	251	194	323
CTGF - ENHO	321	292	128	391	TRIM67 - ENHO	100	352	223	297
CNTFR - ENHO	339	66	205	362	BHLHE41 - ENHO	266	42	276	253
COL10A1 - ENHO	3	274	231	268	MATN4 - ENHO	237	237	197	387
NRN1 - ENHO	282	347	230	199	MAP1B - ENHO	304	227	27	271
PODNL1 - ENHO	98	252	309	316	MATN3 - ENHO	110	233	301	218
CLEC10A - ENHO	340	178	232	378	SLC14A2 - ENHO	205	269	275	322
CNTN6 - ENHO	354	133	220	340	PTPN22 - ENHO	311	283	130	210
FHOD3 - ENHO	366	350	71	300	FAIM2 - ENHO	371	255	169	312
SCN7A - ENHO	150	315	289	269	FOXF2 - ENHO	261	217	163	258
TTC29 - ENHO	351	184	222	334	THBS1 - ENHO	189	247	281	301
SEMA6D - ENHO	372	134	299	272	NKD1 - ENHO	81	238	330	208
FHAD1 - ENHO	376	116	274	363	NXPH2 - ENHO	232	231	352	35
FAM105A - ENHO	203	244	283	55	DAAM2 - ENHO	118	207	268	370
CHRN3 - ENHO	169	383	372	280	MKX - ENHO	113	326	248	379
ADAMTS12 - ENHO	374	68	221	385	VENTX - ENHO	201	363	72	298
PID1 - ENHO	225	358	245	315	ABI3BP - ENHO	111	200	338	338

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between ENHO VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t ENHO with ENHO – > HSPB6 / CCL26 / FMO1 / IGF1 / COL9A2 / LMCD1 / GPC4 / ITGA8 / SEMA5B / SEZ6L / DMC1 / PAK5 / CORO2B / SLC17A7 / TMEM59L / AEBP1 / UNC5B / KAZALD1 / CPE / TRIM2 / BST1 / NRXN2 / SLC35F2 / CUX2 / ST8SIA1 / GHR / CDH6 / NPR3 / PODXL2 / PRG4 / CCN2 / TRIM67 / CNTFR / BHLHE41 / COL10A1 / MATN4 / NRN1 / MAP1B / PODNL1 / MATN3 / CLEC10A / SLC14A2 / CNTN6 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / FAIM2 / SCN7A / FOXF2 / TTC29 / THBS1 / SEMA6D / NKD1 / FHAD1 / NXPH2 / FAM105A / DAAM2 / CHRN3 / MKX / ADAMTS12 / VENTX / PID1 / ABI3BP / PPP2R2B / EXTL1 / CHCHD6 / S100B / VCAM1 / FRZB / NKX6-1 / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / DACT2 / CA3 / MFAP4 / PRRT2 / NT5DC2 / RAB31 / CPT1C / STK32A / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / STARD5 / IL17D / HOXB2 / DNAH12 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS ENHO									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T ENHO									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
PPP2R2B - ENHO	128	242	246	245	EXTL1 - ENHO	247	204	225	350
CHCHD6 - ENHO	369	265	95	228	S100B - ENHO	224	290	343	263
VCAM1 - ENHO	382	243	165	344	FRZB - ENHO	109	249	239	384
NKX6-1 - ENHO	105	296	278	332	F2RL2 - ENHO	258	319	82	325
RHOBTB3 - ENHO	116	388	269	216	DACT2 - ENHO	263	353	262	355
CA3 - ENHO	52	322	217	295	MFAP4 - ENHO	123	229	236	345
PRRT2 - ENHO	243	11	242	260	NT5DC2 - ENHO	204	321	2	246
RAB31 - ENHO	334	44	200	278	CPT1C - ENHO	284	38	297	392
STK32A - ENHO	381	313	270	352	ITGAM - ENHO	60	316	340	236
GPR27 - ENHO	373	173	320	273	MAP6 - ENHO	299	328	339	146
STARD5 - ENHO	331	311	325	114	IL17D - ENHO	36	208	374	251
HOXB2 - ENHO	298	89	317	335	DNAH12 - ENHO	295	387	244	282
FAM131A - ENHO	104	234	364	231	CABP4 - ENHO	322	194	331	289
SLCO3A1 - ENHO	380	267	211	358	BOK - ENHO	359	382	255	262
MYOZ1 - ENHO	239	258	273	274	PDE4DIP - ENHO	342	236	392	51
CIITA - ENHO	195	336	322	207	KCNE1 - ENHO	259	294	375	148
EXT1 - ENHO	260	390	334	239	BGN - ENHO	385	49	345	229
EPHB3 - ENHO	271	223	336	132	NEB - ENHO	28	314	314	227
DUSP5P1 - ENHO	185	377	282	257	ADRA2C - ENHO	234	256	292	18
PRKD1 - ENHO	319	239	290	336	SHC4 - ENHO	379	215	355	48
CYP4Z1 - ENHO	317	366	351	45	C2orf88 - ENHO	355	211	347	66
LDLRAD2 - ENHO	269	240	237	361	ENTPD8 - ENHO	350	278	313	327
NUGGC - ENHO	199	286	349	353	FAM180B - ENHO	315	279	63	211
DACT3 - ENHO	310	384	312	284	SPN - ENHO	220	167	346	244
CLEC9A - ENHO	285	327	342	329	DLGAP2 - ENHO	327	99	252	326
DLL1 - ENHO	357	125	305	234	ZNF521 - ENHO	93	222	218	319
RYR3 - ENHO	386	8	240	365	RNU6-529P - ENHO	305	282	370	103
PLPP4 - ENHO	345	153	227	346	SYT15 - ENHO	301	320	382	198
FAM155A - ENHO	147	372	234	281	GPX3 - ENHO	352	241	228	360
LINC00937 - ENHO	346	378	387	238	ITGB2-AS1 - ENHO	389	261	235	95
LMCD1-AS1 - ENHO	256	60	383	264					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between ENHO VS Individual members.

FAM131A / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CIITA / KCNE1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / NEB / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / C2orf88 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / NUGGC / FAM180B / DACT3 / SPN / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RNU6-529P / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / GPX3 / LINC00937 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic ENHO 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of ENHO-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t ENHO

HSPB6 / CCL26 / FMO1 / IGF1 / COL9A2 ...
LMCD1 / GPC4 / ITGA8 / SEMA5B / SEZ6L ...
DMC1 / PAK5 / CORO2B / SLC17A7 / TMEM59L ...
AEBP1 / UNC5B / KAZALD1 / CPE / TRIM2 ...
BST1 / NRXN2 / SLC35F2 / CUX2 / ST8SIA1 ...
GHR / CDH6 / NPR3 / PODXL2 / PRG4 / CCN2 ...
TRIM67 / CNTFR / BHLHE41 / COL10A1 / MATN4 ...
NRN1 / MAP1B / PODNL1 / MATN3 / CLEC10A ...
SLC14A2 / CNTN6 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / FAIM2 ...
SCN7A / FOXF2 / TTC29 / THBS1 / SEMA6D ...
NKD1 / FHAD1 / NXPH2 / FAM105A / DAAM2 ...
CHRN3 / MKX / ADAMTS12 / VENTX / PID1 ...
ABI3BP / PPP2R2B / EXTL1 / CHCHD6 / S100B ...
VCAM1 / FRZB / NKX6-1 / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 ...
DACT2 / CA3 / MFAP4 / PRRT2 / NT5DC2 / RAB31 ...
CPT1C / STK32A / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 ...
STARD5 / IL17D / HOXB2 / DNAH12 / FAM131A ...
CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP ...
CIITA / KCNE1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / NEB ...
DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 ...
C2orf88 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / NUGGC / FAM180B ...
DACT3 / SPN / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / DLL1 / ZNF521 ...
RYR3 / RNU6-529P / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A ...
GPX3 / LINC00937 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 ENHO

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between ENHO and Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

References

- [1] A. J. Patel, Y.-W. Wan, R. Al-Ouran, J.-P. Revelli, M. F. Cardenas, M. Oneissi, L. Xi, A. Jalali, J. F. Magnotti, D. M. Muzny, et al., Molecular profiling predicts meningioma recurrence and reveals loss of dream complex repression in aggressive tumors, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116 (2019) 21715–21726.
- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] D. N. Louis, A. Perry, P. Wesseling, D. J. Brat, I. A. Cree, D. Figarella-Branger, C. Hawkins, H. Ng, S. M. Pfister, G. Reifenberger, et al., The 2021 who classification of tumors of the central nervous system: a summary, *Neuro-oncology* 23 (2021) 1231–1251.
- [4] S. H. Torp, O. Solheim, A. J. Skjulsvik, The who 2021 classification of central nervous system tumours: a practical update on what neurosurgeons need to know a minireview, *Acta Neurochirurgica* 164 (2022) 2453–2464.
- [5] A. Czarnetzki, E. Schwaderer, C. M. Pusch, Fossil record of meningioma, *The Lancet* 362 (2003) 408.
- [6] D. O. Okonkwo, E. R. Laws Jr, Meningiomas: historical perspective, in: *Meningiomas*, Springer, 2009, pp. 3–10.
- [7] S. Paterniti, Meningiomas surgery in italy in the nineteenth century: Historical review, *Austin Neurosurg Open Access* 2 (2015) 1030.
- [8] Z. Pecchioli, Soria di un fungo della dura madre, operato collestirpazione dal professor zanobi pecchioli, *Nuovo Giornale de’LetteratiScienze* 36 (1838) 39–44.
- [9] H. Cushing, The meningiomas (dural endotheliomas): their source, and favoured seats of origin, *Brain* 45 (1922) 282–316.

- [10] W. contributors, Meningioma — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, 2024. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Meningioma&oldid=1259055917>, online; accessed 11-April-2025.
- [11] M. N. Pamir, P. M. Black, R. Fahlbusch, Meningiomas : a comprehensive text, Elsevier Health Sciences, 2010.
- [12] F. Szulzewsky, H. N. Thirimanne, E. C. Holland, Meningioma: current updates on genetics, classification, and mouse modeling, *Upsala Journal of Medical Sciences* 129 (2024) 10–48101.
- [13] K. G. Kumar, J. L. Trevaskis, D. D. Lam, G. M. Sutton, R. A. Koza, V. N. Chouljenko, K. G. Kousoulas, P. M. Rogers, R. A. Kesterson, M. Thearle, et al., Identification of adropin as a secreted factor linking dietary macronutrient intake with energy homeostasis and lipid metabolism, *Cell metabolism* 8 (2008) 468–481.
- [14] F. Lovren, Y. Pan, A. Quan, K. K. Singh, P. C. Shukla, M. Gupta, M. Al-Omran, H. Teoh, S. Verma, Adropin is a novel regulator of endothelial function, *Circulation* 122 (2010) S185–S192.
- [15] D. Gozal, L. Kheirandish-Gozal, R. Bhattacharjee, H. Molero-Ramirez, H.-L. Tan, H. P. Bandla, Circulating adropin concentrations in pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: potential relevance to endothelial function, *The Journal of pediatrics* 163 (2013) 1122–1126.
- [16] S. Aydin, T. Kuloglu, S. Aydin, Copeptin, adropin and irisin concentrations in breast milk and plasma of healthy women and those with gestational diabetes mellitus, *Peptides* 47 (2013) 66–70.
- [17] L. Li, W. Xie, X.-L. Zheng, W.-D. Yin, C.-K. Tang, A novel peptide adropin in cardiovascular diseases, *Clinica chimica acta* 453 (2016) 107–113.
- [18] L. M. Stein, G. L. Yosten, W. K. Samson, Adropin acts in brain to inhibit water drinking: potential interaction with the orphan g protein-coupled receptor, gpr19, *American Journal of Physiology-Regulatory, Integrative and Comparative Physiology* 310 (2016) R476–R480.
- [19] S. Aydin, M. Yardim, M. Nesimi, M. Yilmaz, M. Kalayci, M. A. Kobalt, O. D. Alatas, T. Cakmak, T. Kuloglu, A. Çelik, et al., Adropin as a potential marker of enzyme-positive acute coronary syndrome, *Cardiovascular journal of Africa* 28 (2017) 40–47.
- [20] F. Gao, J. Fang, F. Chen, C. Wang, S. Chen, S. Zhang, X. Lv, J. Zhang, Q. He, S. Weng, et al., Enho mutations causing low adropin: a possible pathomechanism of mpo-anca associated lung injury, *EBioMedicine* 9 (2016) 324–335.
- [21] A. E. Grzegorzewska, L. Niepolski, A. Mostowska, W. Warchoń, P. P. Jagodziński, Involvement of adropin and adropin-associated genes in metabolic abnormalities of hemodialysis patients, *Life sciences* 160 (2016) 41–46.

- [22] S. Yolbas, M. Kara, M. Yilmaz, S. Aydin, S. S. Koca, Serum adropin level and enho gene expression in systemic sclerosis, *Clinical rheumatology* 35 (2016) 1535–1540.
- [23] W. Hu, L. Chen, Association of serum adropin concentrations with diabetic nephropathy, *Mediators of inflammation* 2016 (2016) 6038261.
- [24] H. Wang, B. Gao, Z. Wu, H. Wang, M. Dong, Alteration of serum adropin level in preeclampsia, *Pregnancy Hypertension: An International Journal of Women's Cardiovascular Health* 8 (2017) 6–8.
- [25] G. Gundogdu, K. Gundogdu, A novel biomarker in patients with knee osteoarthritis: adropin, *Clinical rheumatology* 37 (2018) 2179–2186.
- [26] A. Prystupa, P. Kiciński, D. Luchowska-Kocot, J. Sak, T. Prystupa, K.-H. Chen, Y.-C. Chen, L. Panasiuk, W. Załuska, Afamin and adropin in patients with alcohol-induced liver cirrhosis (2018).
- [27] C. Orsso, A. Butler, M. Muehlbauer, H. Cui, D. Rubin, M. Pakseresht, M. Butler, C. Prado, M. Freemark, A. Haqq, Obestatin and adropin in prader-willi syndrome and nonsyndromic obesity: Associations with weight, bmi-z, and homa-ir, *Pediatric obesity* 14 (2019) e12493.
- [28] O. S. Kwon, R. H. Andtbacka, J. R. Hyngstrom, R. S. Richardson, Vasodilatory function in human skeletal muscle feed arteries with advancing age: the role of adropin, *The Journal of physiology* 597 (2019) 1791–1804.
- [29] S. Korkmaz, G. S. ÖZGÜN, Serum adropin levels in psoriasis vulgaris and its relation with metabolic parameters, *Turkish journal of medical sciences* 49 (2019) 110–115.
- [30] M. Jaszczwili, M. Billert, M. Z. Strowski, K. W. Nowak, M. Skrzypski, Adropin as a fat-burning hormone with multiple functionsreview of a decade of research, *Molecules* 25 (2020) 549.
- [31] Q. Liu, S. Zhang, G. Liu, H. Zhou, Y. Guo, F. Gao, S. Weng, Adropin deficiency worsens tnbs-induced colitis, *International Immunopharmacology* 124 (2023) 110891.
- [32] A. S. Coşkun, M. Bülbül, T. Çeker, A. Özak, G. Tanrıöver, İ. E. Gürer, H. T. Balaban, E. Göksu, M. Aslan, Protective effects of adropin in experimental subarachnoid hemorrhage, *Neuroscience* 551 (2024) 307–315.
- [33] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [34] G. Pujol, B. Iooss, A. Janon, K. Boumhaout, S. Da Veiga, J. Fruth, L. Gilquin, J. Guillaume, L. Le Gratiet, P. Lemaitre, et al., Sensitivity: global sensitivity analysis of model outputs, *R package version 1* (2017).

- [35] H. Huang, Y. Liu, M. Yuan, J. Marron, Statistical significance of clustering using soft thresholding, *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* 24 (2015) 975–993.
- [36] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [37] R. C. Team, R language definition, Vienna, Austria: R foundation for statistical computing 3 (2000) 116.